

Saint Mary's University

Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

RESEARCH CENTER

I. Title: Usability and Acceptability Assessment of "eNay" Barangay Maternal and Child Healthcare Information System (BMCHIS)

II. Abstract

An information system named, eNay Barangay Maternal and Child Healthcare Information System (BMCHIS) was developed to make the recording and reporting of maternal and child healthcare services of barangay health workers in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya easier and faster. It was initially deployed and installed in one (1) barangay of Bayombong. To maximize its utilization and increase the number of barangays that will benefit from eNay BMCHIS, it will be deployed in all barangays of Bayombong. To further improve it, a usability and acceptability assessment was conducted. A three (3) part questionnaire was developed to determine the usability and acceptability of the system. The questionnaire includes items that will determine the frequency of computer usage, computer self-efficacy, eNay BMCHIS's usability and acceptability. The Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) was utilized to assess the system's usability in terms of perceived system usefulness, information quality, interface quality and overall satisfaction. The researchers used frequency, percentage, t-test and Pearson r, mean and standard deviation to analyze the data. Findings revealed that there was a positive relationship between the frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy. The eNay BMCHIS perceived usability was not affected by the respondents' computer self-efficacy. Although the satisfaction rating in all areas of usability criteria was high, the information quality which had the lowest computed rating will have to be improved. Furthermore, the results of the study showed that eNay BMCHIS has a positive usability and acceptability assessment.

Keywords: computer usage, computer self-efficacy, maternal and child healthcare

III. Research Agenda/Domain: Use of ICT software on patient's health data

IV. Name of Proponents: Gertrude G. Danao, PhD (*lead*), Rogie B. Taborda, MIT and Bermelita T. Domingo, MIT

V. Mechanism Applied For: D

VI. Rationale

Computerized healthcare information systems are important nowadays because it is used to help healthcare service providers to deliver their services easier and faster. It is for this reason that, almost in all organizations, be it in private or in public, implement and adopt computerization. However, the development of a computerized information system does not stop with development and installation. After it was installed, a usability assessment should be conducted to assess its usability and improve the system (Hamborg, Vehse and Bludau, 2004). Developers conduct usability assessment because they want to check the quality of the software developed. This is according to Alshamari (2016) and Paz and Pow-Sang (2016), who wrote in their research that the number one attribute of software quality is usability. The ISO 9241-11 defined usability as, "the extent to which any product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified content of use". Furthermore, Assila, de Oliveira and Ezzedine (2016) wrote that usability assessment is used to determine usability problems, satisfaction and acceptability of users. Its results can be used to improve the system and can be used to determine users' satisfaction and acceptability which can be a measure of a product's success. Usability assessment is conducted to determine problems of users which can be on software design, ease of use, ease of learning, satisfaction, error prevention, and help and documentation (Moghaddasi, Rabiei, Adasi, and Ostvan, 2017). In the study of Constantino, Garces and Gajeton (2016), they found that capstone projects or programs of Saint Mary's University (SMU) Bachelor of Science in Information

Computer(BSIT) students that were delivered and deployed, but were not utilized and one of the reasons is it yielded a low usability result. Findings revealed that most of the usability problems that surfaced in their study are on user support and customization.

Using these findings as a guide, the eNay Barangay Maternal and Child Healthcare Information System (BMCHIS) was developed with the Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) in mind. The eNay BMCHIS was developed to effectively and efficiently record important information about their clients and ease their preparation of reports for submission to Municipal Health Office (MHO). It is designed to add, store and update basic information of mother and child; record prenatal and postpartum care; record immunization of child(ren); generate reports on maternal and child data and provide a statistical report of prenatal and child immunization. The system was first deployed or piloted in Barangay District IV of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. It was designed and developed based on the recording and reporting requirements for maternal and child healthcare transactions of BHWs in the Municipality of Bayombong. Corollary to this, the system is planned to be deployed and implemented in all barangays in Bayombong. Prior to deployment and implementation, the researchers aim to conduct a usability assessment of the eNay BMCHIS to determine if the BHW users are satisfied with the system. Furthermore, the usability assessment is also conducted to determine usability problems that can be translated into new requirements for an improved version of the eNay BMCHIS. This research also aimed to determine the acceptability of eNay BMCHIS by determining whether BHW users are willing to use the system or not and that are they recommending its adoption or implementation or not. Furthermore, the researchers conducted a usability and acceptability assessment to determine if eNay BMCHIS would prove useful and acceptable for utilization, not only in Barangay District IV but also in all barangays of Bayombong.

The researchers made use of IBM Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) to conduct the eNay BMCHIS usability assessment. The CSUQ measured eNay BMCHIS's system usefulness, informational quality and interface quality. Specifically, it determined users' satisfaction in terms of effectiveness, efficiency, responsiveness and learnability (Assila, de Oliveira and Ezzedine, 2016; Johnson, Johnston, Crowley, et al., 2011).

VII. Statement of Objectives

This study aimed to conduct a usability and acceptability assessment of eNay BMCHIS.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. determine the profile of barangay health workers or users in terms of
 - a. age
 - b. frequency of computer usage
 - c. computer self-efficacy
2. determine if there is a significant relationship between frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy;
3. determine the perceived usability and acceptability of eNay BMCHIS;
4. determine if there is a significant relationship between computer self-efficacy and perceived usability of eNay BMCHIS; and
5. determine the eNay BMCHIS usability features that need improvement.

VIII. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The age, frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy were gathered to determine if it has an effect with the results of the usability and acceptability assessment of eNay BMCHIS. The age of the respondents were gathered to determine if it affects computer usage. Similarly computer usage was gathered to determine if it has an effect to computer self-efficacy. Studies showed that computer self-efficacy affects usability and acceptability of a software. Hence, the researchers compared self-efficacy with system usability. Furthermore, studies also revealed that users satisfied with a software or a product were accepted for adoption and implementation.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

The age, frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy of the BHW respondents served as inputs for the usability and acceptability assessment that the researchers conducted. The researchers determined if the frequency of computer use and computer self-efficacy are correlated and has an effect on the results of the usability and acceptability assessment conducted. As a pre-requisite for conducting usability and acceptability assessment, the researchers introduced eNay to select BHWs in the different barangays of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. After the training, the usability and acceptability assessment was conducted. The purpose of the assessment was to determine eNay BMCHIS areas for improvement and to determine its acceptability. The Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) was used to determine four (4) criteria of usability, these are the system usability, information quality, interface quality and overall satisfaction of users. The usability criteria with the lowest computed mean result was considered for improvement and was treated as new requirements for an improved or a new version of eNay BMCHIS. An acceptability assessment on the other hand was conducted to determine the adoption and implementation of eNay BMCHIS in their day-to-day operations after the training.

IX. Scope and Delimitation

eNay BMCHIS was designed and developed for the BHWs of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Target beneficiaries of the system are the different barangays of Bayombong. Respondents of the IBM Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) were selected BHWs of each barangay. The CSUQ measures the perceived usability of computer systems like, eNay BMCHIS in terms of effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction of the users. It will also determine the computer system's usability area for improvement. The area for improvement will be treated into new requirements for an improved version of the eNay BMCHIS. The respondents' willingness to adopt or use eNay in their day-to-day operations served as the measure for acceptance of eNay BMCHIS. A development plan for a new version of the eNay BMCHIS was crafted. The acceptability assessment will only focus on the willingness of users to use and recommend the system for adoption and implementation.

X. Significance of the Study

The implementation (installation, deployment, and training of identified users) of eNay BMCHIS to identified barangays in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya would benefit not only the Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) serving in the Municipality of Bayombong, but the whole of Bayombong MHO. Through eNay, recording and reporting of maternal and child healthcare services would be easier and faster. Their reports can easily be prepared, searching of files would be easier and faster, files can also be stored electronically, thus saving papers and office space. Soft or electronic copies of client records and reports can also serve as their back up for paper copies for easy reproduction.

The usability assessment of eNay BMCHIS can identify usability problems which could be an area for improvement. The usability assessment result can point out usability problems that will need fixing or improvement for a better satisfaction rating and acceptability of the eNay BMCHIS, that is, for an assured adoption and utilization.

With the usability assessment, researchers identified usability areas for improvement which can be used for a new version of the existing eNay BMCHIS. As a result of this, the researchers can confidently offer to deploy eNay BMCHIS to other municipalities for a wider adoption and utilization.

XI. Definition of Terms

Acceptability – refers to the attitude or willingness of direct and indirect users to use the eNay BMCHIS.

Computer self-efficacy – refers to the belief or confidence of a person that he/she can use or manipulate a new product or technology.

Direct Users – this refers to the Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) and other health workers who will and are using the eNay BMCHIS.

Frequency of computer usage – refers to how often the users use the computer.

Implementation – this refers to the installation, deployment, and training of users on the use of the system.

Indirect Users - this refers to the Municipal Health Officers who will receive or be given copies of reports generated from eNay BMCHIS.

System – this refers to the eNay Barangay Maternal and Child Healthcare Information System (BMCHIS).

Usability – this refers to the extent to which the system is fit or able to be used.

XII. Review of Related Literature

What is usability assessment?

According to Alshamari (2016) and Paz and Pow-Sang (2016), the number one attribute of a software quality is usability. Usability is defined by as ISO 9241-11 as “the extent to which any product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction. This definition was seconded by Assila, de Oliveira and Ezzedine (2016) and Johnson, Johnston, Crowley, et al (2011) when they wrote that usability assessment is used to determine satisfaction and acceptability of the system and usability problems. Its results can be used to improve the system and can be used to determine users’ satisfaction and acceptability which can be a measure of a product’s success (Moghaddasi, Rabiei, Adasi, and Ostvan, 2017). In fact, researchers like Alshamari (2016) and Paz and Pow-Sang (2016) wrote that usability assessment is conducted to determine the quality of a software. Usability is closely related to quality (Pasha, Abidi and Ali, 2016). It means that the system developed is easy to use and ease of use results to satisfied users. It is for this reason that conducting usability and acceptability assessment is important.

In the study of Assila, de Oliveira and Ezzedine (2016), they have mentioned and compared different usability assessments tools. According to them these usability tools are classified according to the type of system and purpose. These usability tools can be used for universal, website or mobile systems. It can also be used for the purpose of determining usability for post-study, post-task or website. In the end, they have decided that usability tools should be based on the most commonly used criteria of usability. These criteria are in the definition of ISO 9241-11 standard and these are effectivity, efficiency and satisfaction.

According to Zheng et al (2018), a user-friendly interface is far better than a comprehensive users manual. It means that a user display that can easily be understood, easy to memorize and navigate is more preferred by various users of different age and computer exposure or experience. This is a software quality preferred by users. According to them, aside from the user friendliness of the interface, the usefulness of the system is of utmost importance when determining usability. That is, the system should be designed and developed based on the user requirements.

In the study of Gamao and Rebortera (2018), usability is dependent on the availability of the system. According to them, there are issues and concerns in usability when system is not available for use because of down time, response time, and lack of technical support. According to them, these are the common reasons why users are dissatisfied with the system. If it is down, access of the system is compromised. Lack of technical support is also a problem or an issue when it comes to usability. However, the need for technical support can be eliminated if the system is user-friendly as what is written in the study of Zheng et al (2018).

The IBM Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ)

Assila, de Oliveira and Ezzedine (2016) and Johnson, Johnston, Crowley, et al. (2011) in their study and toolkit, respectively, wrote that the IBM CSUQ is one of the standardized non-proprietary usability questionnaire used to determine usability of computerized information systems. The CSUQ is a 19-item questionnaire that has a high reliability of 0.95. It is also used to assess electronic products. CSUQ is for universal type of system and is used for post-study. It is used as an overall assessment of a software that was already deployed and delivered (Sauro and Lewis, 2016). It deals with four (4) general criteria and these are overall system, system usefulness, information and interface quality. It is used to determine the ISO 9241-11 standard on effectivity, efficiency and satisfaction. Lewis (2018) wrote that, CSUQ together with the System Usability Scale (SUS) are the most widely used tool to measure the perceived usability of a system.

Acceptability

According to Sekhon, Cartwright and Francis (2017), acceptability should be considered when designing and developing a system. Acceptability, aside from user satisfaction is a predictor that a system will be adopted and utilized.

Arjadi, Nauta, Bokting (2018) found out in their study that personal innovativeness or the act to try something new is a predictor of acceptability. The use of an application in the internet in their study is new to their respondents. Since it is new, respondents who want to try new things are very willing to try the internet-based system that they have introduced in their study. On the other hand Imus, J.K., Magleo, E., Soriano, A.K., and Olalia, R. Jr. (2018), in their study wrote that since the requirements of the users were met or are present in the system and it is ready to be delivered, the level of users' acceptance of the system is high.

As a result, Arjadi, Nauta, Bokting (2018) and Naslund, Aschbrenner, Marsch and Bartels (2016) made use of acceptability to determine the adoptability and utilization of a system under study. They made use of questions that will determine users acceptability. These questions are: "I intend to use the system." and "I am willing to use the system" as its predictors for acceptability. Naslund, Aschbrenner, Marsch and Bartels (2016) on the other hand used sentences like, "I would like to continue using the system" and "I will recommend the use of the system" to measure acceptability on the use of facebook for health promotion. These questions pertain to willingness to use the system in their work.

User satisfaction

According to (Armstrong, Fogarty, Digsdag and Dimblely (2005) user satisfaction is one factor that will determine the success of a computer-based information system. It measured how the system was able to meet the requirements or needs of the users. In the study of Safdari, Dargahi and Shahmoradi (2011) user satisfaction is a factor that would ensure a systems implementation. As a result, user satisfaction is an important factor in the success of the system, that is, there is a big possibility that the system will be implemented and utilized for its purpose.

Assila, de Oliveira and Ezzedine (2016) in their study wrote that one factor measured in usability assessments is user satisfaction. This is because, a system that meets the users and system requirements and is easy to use results to satisfied users. Users satisfied with a product or a system generally results to a higher acceptability rating thereby, it is implemented and utilized by the organizations and users for which the system was developed.

Self-Efficacy

According to Fathema, Shannon and Ross (2015) self-efficacy directly affects perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Self-efficacy according to them do not refer to the skill but to what one believes of his or her capability to perform or accomplish a particular task. Kass (2014) also wrote that computer self-efficacy has a direct effect on how the respondent perceived the product used. His study revealed that self-efficacy and attitude towards the use of computer has a direct relationship. His study showed that the higher the self-efficacy the higher the accomplishment or performance. Furthermore, Alharbi and Drew (2014) wrote that self-efficacy is a one predictor to utilization. The self-efficacy of users to use the system whether newly introduced to them or not contributes to the acceptance and utilization of the system.

In the study of Rhema, A., and Miliszewska, I. (2014), and Wang, et al. (2019) self-efficacy is one of the factors considered to be crucial for the utilization of a system. It serves as one of the predictors for the acceptability of a software or a system, hence, self-efficacy is included as a variable in

determining a system's acceptability and success. Also, self-efficacy affects the attitude of users towards the use of a system Rhema, A., & Miliszewska, I. (2014).

Related Studies

Why conduct usability and acceptability assessment?

According to Moghaddasi, Rabiei, Asadi and Ostvan (2017), usability assessment is important because it can help in the effective and efficient use of systems. Although according to Kim (2015), usability and acceptability are closely related they are different. According to him, usability pertains to the ability to use or put into operation while acceptability pertains to usefulness, cost, reliability and compatibility. Usability assessment is conducted by the developers to check whether the system meets all the requirements of the users. Aside from this, the ease of use is also evaluated because it contributes to the satisfaction and acceptability of the users. Acceptability although wider in scale needs to be conducted to determine whether a system will be utilized upon delivery. A high usability assessment would result to a better chance of acceptance for utilization.

Lashmari (2016) in his study of evaluating hospital information systems wrote that usability assessment is important because it is a factor that determines the successful implementation of a system. This is because usability assessment entails testing or checking if all the requirements of the users are met and all its functions are running properly for delivery and utilization.

Rizvi, et al. (2017) in their research electronic health record system usability assessment wrote that using a systems development methodology in developing electronic systems is important. Functions of the system should be designed to consider human computer interactions or user interface for the effective and efficient utilization of the system. Human computer interactions consider all the human needs to effectively interact with the system. This includes the color, navigation, placement of buttons, consistency of toolkits and buttons used in the display or interface which will make the system easy to use. The result of the usability assessment will be used to improve the interface of the system. In their study, the usability results were used to improve the system to meet the needs of their user and improve its overall usability.

In the study of Zheng, Rosal and Li (2018) they wrote that a positive response of users in the ease of use of the system is better than a users' manual. That is, a system that is easy to understand, easy to memorize and easy to use will not require the use of a users' manual thereby increasing acceptability.

The goal of each developer when creating or developing a system is for the system to be accepted and utilized. A system to be accepted and utilized, according to Arjadi, Nauta, Bokting (2018), Naslund, Aschbrenner, Marsch and Bartels (2016) and Kim (2015) needs to meet all the requirements of the users, easy to use and is compatible with the operations of the organization. Imus, J.K., Magleo, E., Soriano, A.K., and Olalia, R. Jr. (2018) in their study, made use of the system development life cycle (SDLC) to make sure that they meet the users requirements. Since, systems are borne from needs of the organization a system should run or operate in an environment where the system is developed for. The application of the SDLC in the development of a system helps ensure that the system can be adopted and implemented in the organization the system is built for,

In the study of Constantino, Garces and Gajeton (2016), the capstone project of Bachelor of Science in Information Computer(BSIT) students of Saint Mary's University that were delivered and deployed with low usability level are not utilized. For obvious reasons, their findings also showed that most of the software developed was not utilized because it was not delivered and installed. For the capstone projects or programs that were implemented, problems encountered are on documentation, user support, hardware, training, and customization.

Synthesis

According to authors, mentioned in this study, usability and acceptability assessment is important to determine a system's smooth implementation and adoption. Not only can a usability assessment determine the satisfaction of the users but also, usability problems. Usability can also be understood as "able to use". This may be the reason why usability tests measure the system in terms of system usability, information quality, interface quality and overall satisfaction. This may be the reason why usability tests are conducted before and after deployment of the system. The latter is conducted for improvements or another version. Corollary, the results of a usability assessment can serve as basis for the overall improvement of a system. This is the reason why the researchers conducted the study on eNay BMCHISs' usability and acceptability assessment. Like the study of

Sauro and Lewis (2016), this study made use of the CSUQ which determine the usability of the information system.

Acceptability is the probability that a system will be implemented, adopted and utilized by the users. However, according to researches, self-efficacy also plays as one of the predictors of a system's acceptability. In our study, the researchers measured self-efficacy to determine usability and acceptability results. Studies show that a high self-efficacy results to a bigger chance of acceptability. A system has a bigger chance of adoption and implementation or acceptability when users perceive a system useful. Since researches should be replicated and utilized, the researchers aimed to determine the acceptability of eNay BMCHIS through the questionnaire. Although usability is commonly used interchangeably with acceptability, usability is only a component of acceptability. Acceptability is determined socially and economically. Organizational compatibility is also being considered in acceptability assessments. Thereby, systems with a high usability and acceptability result will yield a high probability of utilization to achieve its purpose.

The IBM Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) is a common tool used to measure the usability of a system, hence this is the tool used to measure the usability of eNay BMCHIS. It is most preferred by researchers because it can measure the effectivity, efficiency and satisfaction of users. Aside from this, it is also a tool that can be used to test usability while the system is being developed, but also after the delivery of the system and training of users.

In determining the usability and acceptability of this study, not only did the researchers measured the usability and acceptability of the system as perceived by the respondents but also included the profile demographics of the respondents. The profile was included to determine if they have an effect or that they have a relationship with other variables like, age vs frequency of computer usage; frequency of computer usage vs computer self-efficacy; and computer self-efficacy with usability.

XIII. Methodology

Research Design

This study followed the basic research processes that made use of quantitative and qualitative data. The researchers distributed a questionnaire to trained BHWs, BNS and MHO representatives to determine eNay BMCHIS's usability and acceptability. A three-part questionnaire was designed to determine the profile of the direct users and their usability assessment of eNay BMCHIS. The first part of the questionnaire gathered the profile of direct users to determine their characteristics of the respondents in terms of age, frequency of use and computer self-efficacy. The computer self-efficacy questions were adopted from the study of Kass (2014). However, the researchers made use of a 4-point Likert scale instead of the 0 to 100 degree of confidence rating scale. The computer self-efficacy used a 4-point Likert scale where "4" means extremely confident, "3" means moderately confident, "2" means slightly confident and "1" means "not confident". The reliability test of the computer self-efficacy using Cronbach alpha is 0.92.

The second part of the questionnaire is the IBM Computer System 19-item Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) adopted from the study of Sauro and Lewis (2016). The third part of the questionnaire composed of questions that determined whether the respondents will recommend and adopt the eNay in their barangay or not.

The computer self-efficacy used a 4-point Likert scale where "4" means extremely confident, "3" means moderately confident, "2" means slightly confident and "1" means "not confident". The reliability test using Cronbach alpha is 0.92.

Samples and Sampling Procedure

All BHW users identified by the MHO of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya were the respondents of the questionnaire on acceptability and usability assessment of eNay BMCHIS.

Research Environment

The locale of the research was all Barangay Health Centers (BHCs) of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. There are twenty-five barangays with BHCs in Bayombong, these are: Bonfal East, Bonfal Proper, Bonfal West, Busilac, Casat, Vista Hills, La Torre North, La Torre South, Magapuy, Magsaysay, Masoc, Paitan, Don Domingo Maddela Poblacion, Don Tomas Maddela Poblacion, Don Mariano Marcos, District IV, Bansing, Cabuaan, Don Mariano Perez, Ipil-Cuneg, Luyang, Salvacion,

San Nicolas, Santa Rosa, and Vista Alegre. The Municipal Health Office of Bayombong located in was also included in its because the research is the usability and acceptability of a barangay maternal and child healthcare information system.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the research were BHWs, Barangay Nutrition Scholars (BNS) and representatives from the MHO of Bayombong.

Research Instrument/Tool

(see XVI: Research Tool)

A three-part questionnaire was designed to determine the profile of the direct users and their usability assessment of eNay BMCHIS. The first part of the questionnaire will gather the profile in terms of age, frequency of computer use, and computer self-efficacy of direct users to determine their characteristics and determine if there will be a difference in terms usability if grouped according to the aforementioned variables. The measure of the frequency of use are the following: (1) once a day; (2) once a week; (3) once a month; and (4) never. The questions to determine the computer self-efficacy of the users was based on a research authored by Kass (2014). The computer self-efficacy questionnaire will determine the degree of confidence in new products like the eNay system. The questionnaire was modified to fit to the study of the proponents. A Likert scale will be used to determine the degree of confidence of the users using the following ratings: (4) extremely confident; (3) moderately confident; (2) slightly confident; and (a) not confident. The second part of the questionnaire is the IBM Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ). It is a 19-item questionnaire that will measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the system and satisfaction of users on the use of the system. A Likert scale will be used to rate the system's effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction of users. This scale range from (4) strongly agree, (3) agree, (2) disagree and (1) strongly disagree. The third part will be questions that will determine if the users and Municipal Health Officers and the BHW users will recommend and adopt the eNay in their barangay.

Treatment of Data

Frequency count and percentage was used to determine the profile of the respondents, particularly on the number of respondents, age, frequency of computer usage and answers to questions under acceptability. T-test was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between (a) age and frequency of computer usage and (b) computer self-efficacy and usability. Pearson r was also used to determine if there is a relationship between frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy of respondents. The mean and standard deviation were used analyze the results of the respondents answers to computer self-efficacy and CSUQ.

XIV. Results and Findings

Section 1: Profile of Respondents

The respondents of the eNay BMCHIS usability and acceptability questionnaire are composed of the following:

Number of respondents

Table 1: Number of respondents

	f	%
Barangay Health Workers (BHWs)	18	64%
Barangay Nutrition Scholar (BNS)	8	29%
Municipal Health Office (MHO) representatives		
Rural Health Midwife	1	4%
Public Health Nurse (PHN)	1	4%
Total	28	100%

The most number of respondents are BHWs of the different barangay in Bayombong followed by the BNS. Despite of this number, only twenty (20) or 80% of the expected twenty-five (25) participants from all barangays of Bayombong participated in the training and answered the questionnaire.

Age group

Table 2: Age of respondents

Age	F	%
20-29	2	7%
30-39	9	32%
40-49	5	18%
50 and above	12	43%
Total	28	100%

Based on the table above, it can be seen that majority of the respondents are aged 51 and above.

Frequency of Computer/Laptop Usage

Table 3: Frequency of computer usage

Frequency	F	%
4 – Everyday	1	4%
3 – Once a week	2	7%
2 – Once a month	9	32%
1 – Never	16	57%

Majority or 57% of the respondents' never used a computer.

Age vs. Frequency of computer usage

Table 4: Age and Frequency of Computer Usage

Age \ freq. of comp. usage	Everyday	Never	once in a week	once a month	Total
20-29	0	0	0	2	2
30-39	0	6	0	3	9
40-49	0	2	2	1	5
50 -above	1	8	0	3	12
Total	1	16	2	9	28

Table 4 shows that majority of the respondents never used a computer. Moreover, it can be observed from the table above that all age group are represented in the column that the frequency of their computer usage is only once a month.

Table 5: t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	Age	Frequency of computer usage
Mean	2.964285714	1.571428571
Variance	1.072751323	0.624338624
Observations	28	28
Pearson Correlation	-0.019395448	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	27	
t Stat	5.605426926	
P(T<=t) one-tail	3.00986E-06	
t Critical one-tail	1.703288446	
P(T<=t) two-tail	6.01973E-06	
t Critical two-tail	2.051830516	

Based on the table above, it can be inferred that the respondents' age and frequency of computer usage is significantly different from each other, therefore we can conclude that these two has no relationship.

Respondents' Self-efficacy

The table below shows the mean of the individual respondent's computer self-efficacy.

Table 5: Respondent's computer self-efficacy

Computer Self Efficacy	<i>f</i>	%
4 – Extremely confident	1	3%
3- Moderately confident	12	43%
2 – Slightly confident	10	36%
1 – Not confident	5	18%

The table above shows that only 43% of the respondents' computer self-efficacy is moderately confident and 36% are slightly confident.

Frequency of Computer Usage vs. Computer Self-Efficacy

The researchers made use of Pearson *r* to determine if frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy are correlated.

Table 6: Pearson *r* result

coefficient <i>r</i>	0.228229
N	28
t-stat	1.195292
Df	26
p-value	0.242762

The coefficient *r* (0.228229) and p-value (0.242762) reveals a weak association between the respondents' frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy. Based on this result, we can conclude that the respondents' frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy has no significant relationship or that computer self-efficacy is independent from their frequency of computer usage. Similarly, we can conclude that the respondents' computer self-efficacy is not a result of their frequency of computer usage.

Section 2: Computer System (eNay BMCHIS) Usability Result

The table below shows the result of the CSUQ of the eNay BMCHIS.

Table 7: eNay BMCHIS usability result

	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
SU1. Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use this system	3.46	0.5	Agree
SU2. It is simple to use this system	3.43	0.49	Agree
SU3. I can effectively complete my work using this system	3.54	0.5	Strongly Agree
SU4. I am able to complete my work quickly using this system	3.54	0.5	Strongly Agree
SU5. I am able to efficiently complete my work using this system	3.5	0.5	Strongly Agree
SU6. I feel comfortable using this system	3.5	0.5	Strongly Agree
SU7. It was easy to learn to use this system.	3.39	0.48	Agree
SU8. I believe I quickly became productive using this system	3.37	0.49	Agree
IQ9. The system gives error messages that clearly tell me how to fix problems.	3.21	0.48	Agree
IQ10. Whenever I make a mistake using the system, I recover easily and quickly	3.22	0.5	Agree
IQ11. The information (such as on-line help, on-screen messages and other documentation) provided with this system is clear.	3.29	0.8	Agree
IQ12. It is easy to find the information I need.	3.57	0.49	Strongly Agree
IQ13. The information provided with the system is easy to	3.57	0.49	Strongly Agree

understand.			
IQ14. The information is effective in helping me complete my work.	3.54	0.5	Strongly Agree
IQ15. The organization of information on the system screens is clear.	3.56	0.5	Strongly Agree
ItQ16. The interface of this system is pleasant.	3.43	0.49	Agree
ItQ17. I like using the interface of this system.	3.41	0.49	Agree
ItQ18. This system has all the functions and capabilities I expect it to have.	3.52	0.5	Strongly Agree
OS19. Overall, I am satisfied with this system.	3.68	0.47	Strongly Agree

It can be observed from the table above that the usability in terms of giving error messages that will tell the user on how to fix the problem, recovering from mistakes and the information or on-screen messages provided in the system had the lowest computed mean. Since these are the items in the CSUQ which yielded low mean result, it shows that these are the usability features that need to be improved in the eNay BMCHIS. These usability features are error messages and help function. According to Saha and Mandal (2015), in case of error messages, there should appear a display that inform the user of what has gone wrong and be presented with possible solutions to solve the error or the wrong activity. A good system should also be able to anticipate the need of the user such as, need for information or help. The help feature should be available when the user wants or needs additional information and/or there is an issue in terms of system behavior. Therefore, a good system should have a function that will help the user achieve what it needs. The help function should be complete, clear and simple for the user to easily understand and follow instructions.

Table 8: *t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means*

	Computer Self-efficacy	Usability
Mean	2.364285714	3.453571429
Variance	0.508306878	0.12776455
Observations	28	28
Pearson Correlation	0.414721743	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	27	
t Stat	-8.844674555	
P(T<=t) one-tail	9.22957E-10	
t Critical one-tail	1.703288446	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.84591E-09	
t Critical two-tail	2.051830516	

The table above shows that there is a weak correlation between the respondents' computer self efficacy with their rate in eNay BMCHIS usability therefore it can not be concluded that the respondents' computer self-efficacy has an effect to the satisfaction rating of the respondents to eNay BMCHISs' usability.

Table 9: *Summary of CSUQ Four (4) Criteria Mean*

Criteria	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. System Usefulness (SU)	3.45	Agree
2. Information Quality (IQ)	3.42	Agree
3. Interface Quality (ItQ)	3.46	Agree
4. Overall satisfaction (OS)	3.68	Strongly Agree

Based on table 2 and 3, the respondents are generally satisfied with the quality of eNay BMCHIS. However, it can also be observed from the aforementioned tables that the information quality criterion needs to be improved. Although it can be observed that the information quality computed mean is still high, that is, 3.42, these criterion needs to be improved because it has the lowest computed mean compared to the other two (2) criterion. The attributes of the information quality are error messages and presence of a help function. Aside from the help function, a user's manual is also perceived as important for it will provide more information on how to effectively manipulate the system and recover from errors

even if there is no one to assist them. Moreover, a manual is helpful as it is used to train users to recognize errors and how to recover from the error. It also serves as a support reference that can be used after training according to Carroll, Smith-Kerker, Ford and Mazur-Rimet (2009). Furthermore, it will also help the users to become more familiar with the features of the eNay BMCHIS for a more efficient use.

It can also be observed that despite of the qualitative description of the three (3) criteria which is only "agree", it can be observed that the overall satisfaction rating or mean had the highest which is 3.68. This shows that in the entirety of the system, the respondents are satisfied with eNay. Studies show that self-efficacy influence satisfaction, that is, a high self-efficacy usually results to a high satisfaction rating. However, it can be observed in this study that for eNay BMCHIS it is not true because in spite of the low or slightly confident computer self-efficacy, the satisfaction rating of is high. Based on the results, it can be deduced that the high satisfaction rating was attributed not from computer self-efficacy but from the high eNay BMCHIS usability criteria results.

Section 3: Acceptability

Table 10: Acceptability Results

Questions	f (%)		Verbatim answers of respondents
	Yes	No	
Do you think eNay can help in the recording and submission of reports for maternal and child care? Why?	28(100%)	0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, to keep records intact. - Yes, because I can clearly do my reports in this systems and I can easily find what I need. - Yes, because mas madaling gawin and less time. - Opo, malaking tulong ito sa pagrerecord naming ng mga clients. Mapapabilis at magiging organize ang bawat data namin. - Yes, kasi madali po ang magrecord ng data
Are you willing to use eNay BMCHIS in your barangay? Why?	28(100%)	0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, for barangay records purposes. - Yes, it can help us so we don't need to write anymore. - Yes, if the barangay can adopt this BMCHIS it is easy for use as a BNS because we have so many reports to do. - Opo, matututo at mapapadali ang aming pagtrabaho sa bawat records.
Will you recommend to other BHWs and other health workers of other barangays the use of eNay BMCHIS? Why?	28(100%)	0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes. - Oo, dahil mahalaga ito para secured and mga reports namin. - Yes, because it help us more at mapadali ang paggawa ng mga reports. - Opo, para pare-pareho kaming mapadali and trabahao o recording ng mga buntis, nanganak at mga nabakunahan or magpapabakuna.

Table 10 shows that all or 100% of the respondents believe that eNay BMCHIS can help them in recording and submission of reports for maternal and child care. Many of them wrote that they believe that eNay can help them make their recording and submission of reports easier and faster. All of them are also willing to use the system and that they will recommend it to other barangay health workers of other barangays to use. One (1) comment from the respondent is that a close coordination with the Municipal Health Office is important, that is, to address concerns or updates about the implementation or use of the system. The results show that barangay health workers of Bayombong will utilize the eNay BMCHIS in the recording and submission of reports of maternal and child care.

XV. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary

A usability and acceptability assessment was conducted by the researchers to further determine needs and improvements of eNay BMCHIS before deploying it to the different barangays and MHO of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. Data on its usability and acceptability was gathered by allowing the respondents to use the system. A questionnaire was used which contained three (3) parts. Part 1 contains questions that will determine the age of the respondents, frequency of use of computer and the tool used to measure the computer self-efficacy of the target users or respondents. Part 2 contains the Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ) that will assess the usability of a system and part 3 consists of questions that will measure the acceptance of the system. The frequency count, percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test and Kruskal-Wallis test were used to analyze the data gathered.

The findings of the study revealed the following:

1. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' frequency of computer usage and age.
2. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' frequency of computer usage and computer self-efficacy.
3. There is weak relationship between the respondents' computer self-efficacy and eNay BMCHIS's usability result.
4. All or 100% of the respondents agreed that eNay BMCHIS's is usable.
5. All or 100% of the respondents accepted eNay BMCHIS for utilization.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn

1. The age of the users does not dictate the frequency of computer usage. There are computer users aged 51 years and above who uses computer more frequently than that of those younger than them.
2. A high frequency of computer usage does not result to a high computer self-efficacy and vice-versa. Furthermore, it is not an assurance that users who do not use computer frequently do not have confidence in using computers or computer-based systems.
3. A high computer self-efficacy does not assure a high system usability result and vice-versa. The confidence of users in using a computer does not have an effect on the systems usability result.
4. eNay BMCHIS is usable and it is accepted for adoption and implementation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended.

1. That other factors or variables be considered in determining frequency of computer usage such as, possession or availability of computer or laptop to use and nature of work.
2. That other factors or variables that can influence computer self-efficacy, such as, educational background be considered.
3. That eNay BMCHIS be adopted and implemented for utilization in all barangays of Bayombong and to other municipalities in Nueva Vizcaya that will request its implementation.

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XVII. Research Tool

Saint Mary's University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Sir/Madam:

We, the proponents are conducting a study on the usability and acceptability of eNay Barangay Maternal and Child Healthcare Information System (BMCHIS). Findings of this study will be used as a basis for future improvements of eNay.

Please answer the questionnaire objectively and honestly. Rest assured that the data gathered from this questionnaire will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you.

Truly yours,

Gertrude G. Danao, Ph.D.
Rogie B. Taborda, MIT
Bermelita T. Domingo, MIT

+++++
Name: _____ (optional)

Part I. Respondents profile. Please put a check on the space provided for your answer.

1. Age:
 - 20-29 30-39 40-49 50 and above
2. Frequency of computer use
 - (4) everyday (3) once a week (2) once a month (1) never

3. Computer self-efficacy
Rate your degree of confidence in using eNay BMCHIS by rating it using the scale given below:

	4 <i>(Extremely confident)</i>	3 <i>(Moderately confident)</i>	2 <i>(Slightly confident)</i>	1 <i>(Not confident)</i>
1. I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if there was no one around to tell me what to do as I go.				
2. I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if I had never used a product like it before				
3. I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if I had only the product manuals for reference				
4. I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if I had seen someone else using it before trying it myself				
5. I feel confident that I could use the				

	new technology even if I could call someone for help if I got stuck				
6.	I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if someone else had helped me get started				
7.	I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if I had a lot of time to complete the job for which the product was provided				
8.	I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if I had just the built-in help facility for assistance				
9.	I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if someone showed me how to do it first				
10.	I feel confident that I could use the new technology even if I had used similar products before this one to do the same job				

Part II. Computer System Usability Questionnaire

Instruction: Please put a check on the column of your answer.

	4 <i>(Strongly Agree)</i>	3 <i>(Agree)</i>	2 <i>(Disagree)</i>	1 <i>(Strongly Disagree)</i>
1. Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use this system				
2. It is simple to use this system				
3. I can effectively complete my work using this system				
4. I am able to complete my work quickly using this system				
5. I am able to efficiently complete my work using this system				
6. I feel comfortable using this system				
7. It was easy to learn to use this system.				
8. I believe I became productive quickly using this system				
9. The system gives error messages that clearly tell me how to fix problems.				
10. Whenever I make a mistake using the system, I recover easily and quickly				
11. The information (such as on-line help, on-screen messages and other documentation) provided with this system is clear				
12. It is easy to find the information I need				
13. The information provided with the system is easy to understand				
14. The information is effective in helping me complete my work				
15. The organization of information on the system screens is clear				
16. The interface of this system is pleasant.				
17. I like using the interface of this system.				
18. This system has all the functions and capabilities I expect it to have.				
19. Overall, I am satisfied with this system.				

Part III. Acceptability questionnaire

- a. Do you think the eNay system will help BHWs in recording and reporting maternal and child healthcare services given/offered or provided in your barangay? (*Sa inyong palagay, makakatulong baa ng eNay system sa inyong pagrerecord o pagrereport sa maternal and childhealthcare services na inyong ginagawa sa inyong barangay?*)
- b. Are you going to use the eNay system in your barangay? (*Gagamitin niyo ba ang eNay sa inyong barangay?*)
- c. Will you recommend the use of eNay to other barangays and to the Municipal Health Office of Bayombong? (*Irerekomenda mo ba ang paggamit ng eNay sa ibang barangay at sa Municipal Health Office ng Bayombong?*)

XVIII. Signatories

Gertrude G. Danao, PhD
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Collaborator

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Collaborator

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University President
